

Research Article

A Study on Sequential Probability Sampling for Monitoring a Resubmitted Lots under Burr-Type XII Distribution

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Abstract

In this research, Sequential probability sampling analysis was used to treat the sample size obtained from either single or double sampling plans. Precisely the research considers and compared the minimum sample obtained from Bur Type XII distribution. Estimations of minimum sample, acceptance and rejection numbers obtained were analyzed and presented to explain the usefulness of sequential plans in relation to single and double sampling plan. Average Sample Number (ASN) obtained indicated the hypothesis at various risks' levels was accepted indicating there is a time limit to terminate the sampling. Sequential probability sampling (SPS) plays a vital role at any sampling plan obtained using Bur Type XII distribution and saves inspection time which was among the major concern of both producers and consumers in the manufacturing industries.

Keywords: Acceptance Sampling Plans, Bur XII, Consumer's risk, Producer's risk, Sequential Probability Sampling.

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Introduction

Acceptance sampling plans are important tools widely used for promoting product quality in the industries. It is an inspection procedure concerned with accepting or rejecting a given lot of large size of products on the basis of its quality after inspection of a sample taken from the lot (Zoramawa *et al.*, 2018a). Single sampling plan is the most popular plan because of its simplicity and ease of administration. Suppose that a lot of size N has been submitted for inspection. A single-sampling plan is defined by the sample size n and the acceptance number c . Each unit in the sample is judged to

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be either conforming or nonconforming. One or several attributes can be inspected in the same sample; generally, a unit that is nonconforming to specifications on one or more attributes is said to be a defective unit. This procedure is called a single-sampling plan because the lot is sentenced based on the information contained in one sample of size n .

Double sampling plans are characterized by two sample sizes along with two sets of acceptance and rejection numbers. The two samples may or may not be equal, but in most applications the second sample size is either equal to the first or twice the first. The procedure calls for a sample of size n_1 to be taken. If the number of nonconforming items is equal to or less than the first acceptance number c_1 , the lot is accepted. If the number of nonconforming items is equal to or greater than c_1 but less than c_2 then a second sample of size n_2 is taken. Now if the number of nonconforming items from the total n_1+n_2 items is less than c_2 , the combined acceptance number for the two samples, the lot is accepted. If there are $c_2 + 1$ items nonconforming, the lot is rejected (Wadsworth *et al.*, 2004).

Sequential analysis is a method of statistical inference whose main feature is that the number of observations or samples required by the procedure is not determined in advance. The decision to end the sampling depends, at each stage, on the results of the samples already taken. An advantage of this type of testing is that on average a smaller number of trials are needed to make a decision, in relation to an equally reliable test with a predetermined number of observations.

The SPRT was initially developed by (Wald, 1947) for quality control problems during World War II. It has many extensions and applications: such as in clinical trial and in quality control. The original development of the SPRT is used as a statistical device to decide which of two simple hypotheses is more correct. Wald's SPRT is currently the only Bayesian Statistical procedure in SISA (Prasad *et al.*, 2015). What is required in Bayesian statistics is quite a detailed description of the expectations of the outcome under the model prior to executing the data collection. In Wald's SPRT, if certain conditions are met during the data collection decisions are taken with regard to continuing the data collection and the interpretation of the gathered data. Wald's procedure is particularly relevant if the data is collected sequentially. Sequential Analysis is different from Classical Hypothesis Testing where the number of cases tested or collected is fixed at the beginning of the experiment. In Classical Hypothesis Testing the data collection is executed without analysis and consideration of the data. After all data is collected the analysis is done and conclusions are drawn. However, in Sequential Analysis every case is analyzed directly after being collected, the data collected up to that moment is then compared with certain threshold values, incorporating the new information obtained from the freshly collected case (ibid).

This approach allows one to draw conclusions during the data collection, and a final conclusion can possibly be reached at a much earlier stage as is the case in Classical

Hypothesis Testing.

Since the 18th century there has been a growing interest in statistical hypothesis testing. In literatures, several theories have been already proposed to extend the applicability of the mathematical background or to optimize calculation (Gardonyi *et al.*, 2019).

However, new methodologies (Xian *et al.*, 2017a), (Li *et al.*, 2017b), and (Rasay *et al.*, 2018) of statistical hypothesis tests are published every year. A test can solely be called sequential, if the number of observations is not predetermined, but it is dependent on the outcome of the observations (Gardonyi *et al.*, 2019).

Various sampling plans and sequential tests have also been proposed for testing different hypotheses for example (Zoramawa *et al.*, 2018b) in their research on Double Acceptance Sampling Plans Based on Truncated Life Tests for the Inverse Rayleigh Distribution, double acceptance sampling plans was developed using the Inverse Rayleigh Distribution (IRD) as a model for the life time random variable for a truncated life test. In their paper, the single acceptance sampling developed by (Rosaiah & Kantam, 2005) was extended to double acceptance sampling in terms of finding the minimum number of sample sizes necessary to ensure the specified average life time under a given consumer's risk. The probability of acceptance using the cumulative distribution function of IRD was calculated for different consumer's confidence levels with fixed producer's risk. The operating characteristic curves of the sampling plans as well as the tables were presented.

The double acceptance sampling plan using percentile developed by (Zoramawa *et al.*, 2018a) was truncated at a pre-specified time. Reasoned that population mean used in most researches can be influenced mostly by the extreme values and as such may not satisfy the requirement for most life related distributions; moreover, most of the employed life distributions were not symmetric (Rao, 2012). (Darkhovsky, 2011) studied the problem of sequential testing for two composite hypotheses by proposing a sequential procedure which minimizes the Bayesian risk maximal over a family of prior parameter distributions. (Kharin, 2016) investigated the performance and robustness of sequential tests. A sequential testing procedure proposed by (Nakamura *et al.*, 2016) to determine the minimum dose with a threshold effect.

A universal sequential test for detecting outliers among all collected observation sequences was proposed (Li *et al.*, 2017b) and (Prasad *et al.*, 2015) in their paper uses a well-known test procedure of statistical science called as Sequential probability sampling (SPS) is adopted for Burr Type XII model in assessing the reliability of

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developed software. In their research, SPRT requires considerably less number of observations when compared with the other existing testing procedures. Hence Sequential Analysis of Statistical Science could be adopted to decide upon the reliable/unreliable of the developed software very quickly. The paper proposes the performance of SPRT on Interval domain data using Burr type XII model and analyzed the results by applying on 6 data sets. The Maximum Likelihood Estimation is used for estimation of parameters.

(Xian *et al.*, 2017a) in their paper considered the problem of testing two separate families of hypotheses via a generalization of the sequential probability ratio test. The generalized likelihood ratio statistic is considered and the stopping rule is the first boundary crossing of the generalized likelihood ratio statistic. The result shows that this sequential test is asymptotically optimal in the sense that it achieves asymptotically the shortest expected sample size as the maximal type I and type II error probabilities tend to zero.

Rasay, *et al.* (2018) comes up with a procedure for computing the operation characteristic curve and average sample number (ASN) in their proposed Sequential Sampling plan. A repetitive group sampling plan and a double sampling (DS) plan were also designed based on the truncated life test. Performance of the SS plan was compared with the DS plan and repetitive sampling plan. The applications of these three sampling plans were illustrated in the industry using a real example. The results of the comparison study indicate that the proposed SS plan has a better performance and could significantly reduce the ASN.

The ability to potentially reduce the sample size required to make a decision in an experiment has numerous applications because it leads to the conserving of resources, making funding easier to appropriate (Opperman & Ning, 2019). Sequential probability ratio test was an extension of single and double sampling plan that determine the minimum number of observations required to terminate a sample. (Aslam *et al.*, 2011) proposed a GASP for resubmitted lots under Burr-type XII distributions at various group number g , consumer's risk β and constant producer's α . The result requires minimum number of observations to terminate the sample and this could be determined using SPRT. This saves sampling time which was among the major concern of both producers and consumers during sampling in the manufacturing industries.

The main objective of this paper was to determine the minimum number of sample size required to run a GASP for resubmitted lots under Burr-type XII distribution using SPRT hypothesis in comparison with ASN.

The general Hypothesis at $\beta = 0.25, 0.10, 0.05$ or 0.01 and $\alpha = 0.05$ was stated as:

$$H_0: p = p_0 = 0.05$$

$$H_1: p = p_1 = 0.20$$

Methodology

In this research, we consider the parameters of the proposed sampling plan developed by Aslam under GASP for resubmitted lots under Burr-type XII distributions at various group number g , consumer's risk β and constant producer's α . These parameters include the power of the test $P^* = 1 - \beta$, which determine the consumers risk, the specified producers risk α and the maximum values of n at various sampling categories of the sampling output at differing power levels.

Hypothesis was tested at each consumers risk level β with the existed powers $1 - \beta$, produces risk α and the maximum sampling number n_i ($i = 1, \dots, 4$) number of β s. The SPRT limits for each hypothesis was computed and plotted by assigning SPRT null hypothesis $H_0: p = p_0$ with alternative hypothesis $H_1: p = p_1$.

ASN values were computed at $p = 0$ and 1 . These values were compared with the maximum n_i values in order to decide whether to accept, reject or no decision on the ongoing sampling. The SPRT graph gives a pair of parallel line of d_1 and d_2 which if at any stage, n_i values falls above or below the lines, we then accept or reject the sampling respectively. This helps the experimenter to terminate the sampling and takes decision.

Sequential Probability Ratio Test

A sequential probability sampling (SPS) is a hypothesis test for sequential samples. (Glen, 2021)

Sequential sampling works in a very non-traditional way; instead of a fixed sample size, you choose one item (or a few) at a time, and then test your hypothesis. You can either:

- Reject the null hypothesis (H_0) in favor of the alternate hypothesis (H_1) and stop,
- Keep the null hypothesis and stop,
- Fail to reach either conclusion and continue sampling.

If you fail to reach a conclusion, you repeat the sampling and then the hypothesis test. You keep on repeating this process until you have a sound conclusion, so you don't know the how big your sample will be until you're finished testing (Glen, 2021).

Subject to the power requirement, the hypothesis is tested as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} H_0: p &= p_0 \\ H_1: p &= p_1 \end{aligned}$$

Consider the ratios

$$R(n, x) = \frac{f(x, p_0)}{f(x, p_1)} \tag{1}$$

where $f(x, p)$ is the probability function which can be either Binomial, Poisson, or Hypergeometric.

$$\text{Let } g_1 = \log_{10} \left(\frac{LTPD}{AQL} \right) \text{ and } g_2 = \log_{10} \left(\frac{1-AQL}{1-LTP} \right) \tag{2}$$

where $AQL = p_0$ and $LTPD = p_1$ with

$$\begin{aligned} a &= \log_{10} \left(\frac{1-\beta}{\alpha} \right) \\ b &= \log_{10} \left(\frac{1-\alpha}{\beta} \right) \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

We have

$$\begin{aligned} h_1 &= \frac{b}{g_1 + g_2} \\ h_2 &= \frac{a}{g_1 + g_2} \end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

where $g_1 + g_2 = k$

$$\begin{aligned} g_1 &= \frac{\log_{10} \left(\frac{1-\alpha}{\beta} \right)}{k} \text{ and} \\ g_2 &= \frac{\log_{10} \left(\frac{1-\beta}{\alpha} \right)}{k} \end{aligned}$$

$$s = \frac{g_2}{g_1 + g_2} \tag{5}$$

$$\begin{aligned} d_1 &= -h_1 + s_n \\ d_2 &= h_2 + s_n \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

Using equations 2-6, the required regions can be computed and plotted for decision making based on SPS.

To determine the region for decision, we consider the following areas

$$\begin{aligned} i) & -h_1 + sn < x < h_2 + sn \\ ii) & x_a \leq -h_1 + sn \\ iii) & x_r \geq h_2 + sn \end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

Accept the lot if (ii) reject the lot if (iii) and continue inspection if it is (i).

Average Sample Number (ASN)

The ASN can be plotted from the following fixed points:

$$ASN = \left(\frac{h_1}{s}, \frac{(1-\alpha)h_1 - \alpha h_2}{(s-p_0)}, \frac{h_1 h_2}{s(1-s)}, \frac{(1-\beta)h_2 - \beta h_1}{p_1 - s}, \frac{h_2}{1-s} \right), \text{ for } p = 0, p_0, s, p_1 \text{ and } 1 \text{ respectively.}$$

Decision was taken as shown in Fig. 1 below by using average sample number (ASN) values obtained at $p = 0$ and 1 in order to accept when $n_i (i = 1, \dots, 4) \geq \frac{h_1}{s}$, to reject when $n_i (i = 1, \dots, 4) \geq \frac{h_2}{1-s}$ or to continue sampling when $n_i (i = 1, \dots, 4) < \min \left(\frac{h_2}{1-s}, \frac{h_1}{s} \right)$.

The sample size obtained from (Aslam *et al*, 2011) having $w = 2$ under Burr-type XII with $k = 0.08$ and $b = 5.47$ for 10th percentile with β , maximum number of g 's (n) With constant $\alpha = 0.05$, $p_0 = AQL = 0.05$ and $p_1 = LTPD = 0.2$ is shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Sample size by GASP

s/n	Power		No. of exp.
	$1 - \beta$	β	Min n
1	0.75	0.25	10
2	0.90	0.10	14
3	0.95	0.05	20
4	0.99	0.01	30

Results

The sample size obtained from SPS is presented in Table 2. Average Sample Number (ASN) result for β , maximum number of gs (n) With constant α , p_0 and p_1

Table 2: Sample sizes by SPS

h_1	h_2	ASN	$p = 0$	$p = p_0$	$p = s$	$p = p_1$	$p = 1$
0.85679	1.739	ASN1	7.768519	12.05839	15.18351	-	1.954569
1.44485	1.85501	ASN2	13.10046	21.22835	27.31286	-	2.08496
1.88971	1.88971	ASN3	17.13401	28.20931	36.39054	-	2.123962
2.92263	1.91618	ASN4	26.4995	44.46325	57.07006	-11.718	2.153713

SPS plots at power $P^* = 1 - \beta = 0.70, 0.10, 0.95, 0.99$, Lower proportion (AQL) $p_0 = 0.05$, Higher prop.(LTPD) $p_1 = 0.20$, max $n = 10, 14, 20$, and 30

Fig. 2: SPS plot at power $P^* = 1 - \beta = 0.70$, Lowerprop. (AQL) $p_0 = 0.05$, Higherprop.(LTPD) $p_1 = 0.20$, min $n = 8$

Fig. 3: SPS computation at power $P^* = 1 - \beta = 0.10$, Lowerprop. (AQL) = $p_0 = 0.05$, $p_1 = 0.20$, min $n = 14$.

Fig 4.: SPS computation at power $P^* = 1 - \beta = 0.95$, Lowerprop. (AQL) $p_0 = 0.05$, Higher prop.(LTPD) $p_1 = 0.20$, min $n = 18$

Fig. 5: SPRT computation at power $P^* = 1 - \beta = 0.99$, Lowerprop. (AQL) = $p_0 = 0.05$, Higher prop.(LTPD) = $p_1 = 0.20$, max $n = 30$.

The results as shown from Figs 2 & 3 for the four tested hypothesis using sequential probability sampling SPS indicated that the sample sizes obtained from GASP were greater than the sample sizes from SPS. For example, Fig. 4 indicates the minimum size to be inspected as per that plan to be 18 while for the GASP it was 20; likewise Fig. 5 indicates the minimum size to be inspected to be 27 whereas GASP reported 30 as the minimum. This proves that the plan is capable of reducing inspection time and cost.

Conclusion

The main objective of this paper was to determine the minimum number of sample size required to make a decision. In the developed GASP for resubmitted lots under Burr-type XII distribution, SPS shows that a decision can be made at the sample size (n) smaller than that of GASP. The plan by SPS usually decreases sample size as such both the producer and consumer can be satisfied because the decision to reject the lot is not easy at the same time decision to accept the bad lot is also difficult. With this development, both the parties are save from making a hasty decision with minimum cost.

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